

This document aims to clarify the codes used in Dr Metin Koca's draft article entitled **“Networked Social Movements and Radicalisation: Yellow Vests’ cross-ideological horizon for underrepresented groups.”**

Appendix

Based on the PRIME Youth ERC project's coding manual (Benevento, Koca and Kaya 2022)¹, the project interviews are coded into twelve principal codes and 157 sub-codes that saturate each bullet point. While the coding manual assumes that each code represents a value, the given article goes beyond normative statements and reviews the coding material in the form of knowledge claims (e.g., why do Yellow Vests fail/succeed) and personal experiences (e.g., why not joining Yellow Vests despite supporting them). After this re-interpretation, the codes became helpful in analysing the contours of political underrepresentation, the demands for socialisation with other political orientations, and the ideational and material limits to organisational activity.

The starting point of the given article is its inclusion of politically underrepresented individuals. To measure the accuracy of this case selection, Koca identifies 16 codes that relate to the underrepresented political stance of the PRIME Youth interlocutors. After combining value expressions, knowledge claims and personal experiences, these codes shall be paraphrased as follows:

Strong interest in FR Politics: Having strong political opinions and expressing interest in French politics.

Disinterest in FR Politics: Lacking curiosity or attention to political news about French politics. This code does not necessarily involve negative connotations about politics.

Discontent with FR Politics: Emphasising displeasure with the current political parties/figures, recognising one's political grievances.

Anything Positive about FR Government: Emphasising one's satisfaction with the Macron government (the government of the period in which the Yellow Vests were active).

Challenging Mainstream Views: Expressing an interest in challenging the mainstream conduct of politics or the arguments about it.

Voting is necessary: Identifying the act of voting as a necessity for one's well-being.

Voting does not work: Acknowledging the unacceptably limited power voting has in the French political system.

Membership in an organisation: Acknowledging the importance of membership to organisations (clubs, associations, social movements etc.).

¹ Benevento, Ayşenur, Metin Koca, and Ayhan Kaya. 2022. “Coding Manual: Nativism, Islamophobia and Islamism in the Age of Populism.” *ISLAM-OPHOB-ISM ERC Project (Number 785934)*. doi: [10.5281/zenodo.6976652](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6976652).

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Mistrust in Politics: Voicing disbelief towards the political system and the existing ways of politics in France.

Protests are Important: Participating in or acknowledging the value of street demonstrations.

Protests are Useless: Seeing little or no decisive power in street demonstrations. This code includes a disturbance or dissatisfaction with their efficiency.

Supports Protests with No Participation: Recognising the merit of street demonstrations despite not participating in them (e.g., due to habitual reasons, lack of courage, or other means necessary to participate in a protest).

Illegal Action is Justifiable: Interpreting illegal action as acceptable or considerable in pursuit of one's ideological aims.

Caveats about Illegal Act: Acknowledging the function of law or morals against illegal activism.